

Effects of Shared First Language and Speakers' First Language on Comprehensibility of Paired Interaction

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Few spoken learner corpora are easily accessible to the public and young researchers. Given this reality, graduate students whose research interests include spoken interaction face difficulty developing study stimuli that include conversational data. Utilizing the paired interaction samples from the Wildcat Corpus of native- and foreign-accented English (XYZ), the current study investigated how the differing degrees of shared first language between listeners and speaker pairs affect L1-English listeners' comprehensibility. Specifically, the research questions the study aimed to explore are as follows: (1) To what extent does the shared L1 status affect English-L1 listeners' comprehensibility scores? (2) To what extent does the speakers' L1 background affect English-L1 listeners' comprehensibility scores? Speakers consisted of three groups: (a) L1-fully shared pairs (English-English pairs); (b) L1-partially shared pairs (English-Chinese pairs, English-Korean pairs); and (c) L1-not shared pairs (Chinese-Chinese, Korean-Korean, and Chinese-Korean pairs). Speakers participated in a spot-the-difference task called the Diafix task, which was designed to elicit a spontaneous dialogic interaction between two speakers. Thirty English-L1 listeners listened to the excerpts of paired interaction and provided the scalar ratings of their comprehensibility. A mixed-effects model indicated that the listeners rated the L1-fully shared group and the L1-partially shared group as highly comprehensible. However, their comprehensibility ratings were significantly lower when they listened to L1-not shared pairs ($p = .028$). Results have implications for language teaching and learning and spoken communications in global contexts. Furthermore, the study will give ideas for graduate students on applications of the currently available spoken corpora for designing a study on second language acquisition.

Reference

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